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LIFELONG LEARNING THROUGH OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES

Nagaiah M¹, Dr. Thanuskodi S²

¹Research Assistant/ Research Scholar, ²Head of the Department
DLISc, Alagappa University, TamilNadu, India.
nagaiahben@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The idea that everyone should continue to learn throughout their life has been made feasible by open educational resources (OER). Open educational resources are easily accessible and cost-free to people from all walks of life. Additionally, it grants the individual complete freedom to keep it to himself, alter it as he pleases, or redistribute it as he sees fit. UNESCO initially coined the phrase "open educational resources" (OER) in 2002 to refer to educational resources that can be openly accessed, reused, modified, and shared in order to raise the calibre of curricula and instruction and lower costs (UNESCO,2002). The first OERs (Open Education Resources) were created more than twenty years ago. New waves of OER initiatives, such as MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses), are creating new frontiers for outdoor education and higher education. Various development and distribution approaches are currently being proposed (Yamada,2014). In order to shed light on the changes that have occurred in OER as current events and how its use of alternatives is among the people, this study evaluates the changes that OER has made to the world population thus far as well as earlier research articles.

Keywords: Lifelong learning, continues learning, virtual resources, ICT, Information communication technology, Open Educational Resources, OER's, Open Access, Open Education, Open License, MOOC, Usage of OER.

INTRODUCTION

In order to encourage our enthusiasm in studying while generally enjoying lifelong learning and continuing university continuing education, Open Educational Resources and Its continuing classes are set us up for success. Additionally, it imparts a particular learning consumption at regular intervals so that everyone may simply grasp its essence. It is more or less obvious that education and university-related continuing education in general will continue to be valued throughout life. Lifelong learning is promoted as a solution to the problems posed by population growth, new technologies, and globalisation because it is at the top of the political agenda (Dinevski,2008). The learning process is supported by a wide range of interactions when it is conducted online or in a virtual environment, particularly with student-student or student-teacher interactions, as well as teacher, individual, and group interactions to share learning resources and other information. The idea of learning networks or communities is now emerging (Mulder,2007). By permitting open licences for objects to get creative commons licences through transparency and freedom in the use of educational materials, the open education resources (OER) movement has allowed educators to become more imaginative in their teaching techniques (Sandanyake,2019). There are five main obstacles to utilising OER, despite the fact that there are several opportunities for a person to learn throughout his or her life: Lack of institutional support for accessing open educational resources (OER), a lack of technology means for resource sharing and diversity, a lack of user skills and time, inadequate or subpar resources, and personal problems including trust and time constraints (Halder, 2019).

Definition of Open Educational Resources

The following is a definition of open educational resources provided by the William and Flora Hewlett Foundation:

Teaching, learning, and research resources known as open educational resources (OER) are those that are either in the public domain or have been published under a licence that allows for their unrestricted

use and repurposing by others. Full courses, course materials, modules, textbooks, streaming videos, exams, software, and other tools, materials, or approaches used to enable access to knowledge are all examples of open educational resources.

Open Educational Resources licenses

The public domain or sources released under an intellectual property licence that permits their unrestricted use and re-use by others are what OERs are, it is important to keep in mind. The so-called Creative Commons License, which permits unrestricted use and repurposing, is the intellectual property licence that is most frequently applied to OER. In accordance with copyright regulations, creative commons licences immediately provide usage rights for that work.

Need of the study

According to UNESCO, there are more than 1.5 billion pupils in 165 countries, and 87% of them are at risk of becoming infected with the COVID-19 pandemic. Students can stay in school in these circumstances with the aid of open educational resources. In 2020, Nagaiah, and Thanuskodi. The current state of college students is made more difficult by a lack of sufficient funds, resources, and labour. The purpose of this study is to describe how open educational resources (OERs) might benefit higher education, and in particular, how they can boost enrolment rates. OER gives information resources about educational growth in India as well as resources from various educational institutions. Additionally, this OER aids in providing information for improving knowledge and lifetime learning.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

To automatically extract the knowledge components of educational materials for their study, Bulathwela and colleagues (2020) used a Wikipedia-based ontology and a selection of well-known online Bayesian tactics inspired by the proposed item response theory and cognitive tracking domains. The proposal, True Learn, concentrates on those suggestions. The subject offers enough innovations to assist the learner increase their understanding of the subject and keep them involved. The learner has adequate background knowledge (so they can grasp and master the information). Additionally, they created a sizable open educational video archive and evaluated the effectiveness of the suggested algorithms, demonstrating a great potential for creating a powerful education recommendation system.

In their study, Lim et al. (2017) came to the conclusion that both MOOCs and OER guarantee open, plentiful, inclusive, and cost-free services. Introducing a new paradigm in education are MOOCs and OER. Institutions, governments, and private investors from all over the world wanting to establish their brands and enter the education and training industry have taken notice of MOOCs' growing popularity. The growth of an enthusiastic community of developers, educators, and users in Singapore and other parts of the world is evidence of OER's appeal. Even though MOOCs and OER have potential, it's necessary to be aware of the ramifications and restrictions that these new developments also entail. It can be instructive to take a closer look at MOOCs and OER in Singapore, as well as how they have affected national and societal policy and legislation.

Is it viable to use integrated e-learning for Life Long Learning (LLL)? has been summarised by Nantha (2011). According to the evaluation of the learners, this would be feasible. Since learners may self-manage their own learning without having to quit their jobs or adhere to other restrictions, integrated e-learning to support LLL appears to be more promising. To the extent that e-learning replaces classroom instruction as the main method of learning, however, the model still has to be clarified and improved.

OBJECTIVES

- To motivate lifelong learning with OER among different users.
- To look into how open educational resources (OER) might help different users support lifelong learning.
- To identify the online contexts that influence OER learning and interaction.
- To examine what users value most in learning with OER.

- To find the needs and interests of various users of OER.

METHODOLOGY

This study used a broad descriptive review method, which is generally used to provide the much-needed bridge between broad and other related articles under one heading, and to combine multiple studies on different topics for interpretation or interconnected purposes (Baumeister, 1997). The study is useful for providing this type of updated literature and can be used to summarize, coordinate, draw conclusions, identify research gaps, and make recommendations for future research (Cronin et al., 2008). By exploring the concept of how OERs were used and the lifelong knowledge of the learner will help address the economic and community demands. OER-based learning supports a reflective and participatory learning process through academic principles and open education practices (OEP).

OER IN LIFELONG LEARNING

Open education resources help with lifelong learning in many forms. They cater to all the educational needs of the society in various dimensions. We will see what they are in the following sources.

Open journal articles

Figure 1 is the home page of DOAJ. In 2003, 300 open access journals were included in the DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals). Nearly 17,500 open-access, peer-reviewed journals in all fields of science, technology, health, social sciences, the arts, and humanities are now included in this independent database. All nations and languages' open access journals are accepted for indexing. Numerous libraries, publishers, and other like-minded groups give DOAJ financial assistance. Supporting DOAJ shows a steadfast dedication to open access and the systems that underpin it. The fundamental standards for inclusion in the DOAJ are based on the ideals of transparency and best practise in scholarly publication, of which DOAJ is a co-author.

Figure 1 – Homepage of DOAJ (<https://doaj.org/>)

The Core website is referenced in Fig. 2. It holds the largest collection of open-access academic publications in the world and offers useful services for businesses, initiations, and researchers. More than 207255818 research papers from all across the world are included.

Figure 2 – Homepage of Core (<https://core.ac.uk/>)

Books

Open Access books, often known as OER books, are accessible for free download and usage. The list of websites is provided below

- | | |
|-------------|---|
| OPENSTAX | - https://openstax.org/ |
| Open Oregon | - https://openoregon.org/tag/textbooks/ |
| OAPEN | - https://www.oapen.org/ |
| Book Boon | - https://bookboon.com/ |
| INTECHOPEN | - https://www.intechopen.com/ |
| LIBRE TEXTS | - https://libretexts.org/ |

Fig -3 shows the wiki book this is an open-content textbook collection that anyone cans edit.

Fig-3: Homepage of Wiki Book (https://en.wikibooks.org/wiki/Main_Page)

Open Multimedia

The Creative Commons licence governs any freely available designs that can be downloaded. The user is completely free to download most of the material they require for themselves and permit its public sharing or redistribution. Open Multimedia includes a wide range of media formats that are subject to open licence. These can be tools like high-resolution photos that can be downloaded, website templates, and stock video. However, since rules and limits may still be in place, it is crucial to abide by the licence that is associated with the work. Figure 4 is one such example.

Figure 4 – Homepage of Freestock

Open Simulation/Virtual Lab

Virtual laboratories and simulations are technologies that give students a place to interact with their subject matter (fig. 5). Faculty can use it as a collection of labs and simulations in a distance learning setting. Although most are science-related, there are some resources for fields outside of science. The list below includes a few free simulation websites.

- APA online Psychology laboratory -<https://opl.apa.org/>
- MERLOT -<https://www.merlot.org/merlot/>
- PHET -<https://phet.colorado.edu/>

Figure 5 – Homepage of Lab X change (<https://www.labxchange.org/>)

Open Courses

A high-quality digital distribution of educational resources at the college and university levels is called Open Courseware (OCW). These resources are arranged into courses and frequently contain tools for course planning and evaluation in addition to thematic content. Open Courseware is freely available, publicly licenced content that is always online and available to anybody (fig. 6). Following are some websites with open courseware.

Saylor Academy	- https://www.saylor.org/
OERU	- https://oeru.org/
Khan Academy	- https://www.khanacademy.org/
Open Course Library	- https://www.openwa.org/open-course-library/
Open learning Initiate	- https://www.openlearning.com/

Figure 6 - MIT open courseware (<https://ocw.mit.edu/index.htm>)

OER Repositories

The OER Repositories are the places to give information under the OER. There are some OER Repositories websites that are followed.

OER Commons	- https://www.oercommons.org/
Open Learn	- https://www.open.edu/openlearn/
OPENSTAX	- https://openstax.org/
OPENUPED	- https://www.openuped.eu/

OER search Engines

Using search engines to find information is really helpful. Search engines support the use and reuse of academic and instructional materials in the context of open educational resources (OER). The top search engines for open educational resources are included in this paper, both globally and for the particular topic areas covered by the UOC. Here are a few examples of open educational resource (OER) search engines:

cc search	- https://search.creativecommons.org/
Mason OER METAFINDER	- https://oer.deepwebaccess.com/oer/desktop/en/search.html
OASIS	- https://sourceforge.net/projects/oasisse/
OER Commons	- https://www.oercommons.org/
I EEE XPLORE	- https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7389750

OER initiatives in India

In India, the government has made numerous efforts to support and promote the idea of open education. Open resources based on repositories, libraries, instructional media files, and e-books were first intended to be made available. All people had access to these. IGNOU's National Digital Repository launched some of these initiatives by creating a section specifically tasked with increasing student access to education. A few well-known names along this route are the various colleges and universities offering the Education and Research Network (ERNET) connection; EDUSAT, an educational satellite launched in India that makes use of television to disseminate academic information to the Confederation for Educational Relations (CEC); Information and Library Network Center (INFLIBNET) for Autonomous Universities for Linking University Libraries, and has launched several pro-education initiatives. These are initiatives for open learning and education using technology that MOOCs have not yet reached. India too began developing online courses after the concept was developed. The government introduced the e-PG Pathshala in 2013, specifically for postgraduate programmes run by UGC's INFLIBNET. Chanahan (2017)

CONCLUSION

Population growth around the world has many consequences. As a result, unemployment is rising. Parents have to pay huge sums to provide education for their children. This OER plays a huge role in overcoming this. The reason most people do not use it is that there is not enough awareness about OER among different users to promote lifelong learning with OER. Much more awareness programmes and other activities are needed in the ways many people use them. The role of open education resources (OERs) in enhancing lifelong learning among different users is significant. Information Communication technology devices such as laptops and computer equipment are essential to using OER, but their cost is high, so the government can provide such devices to economically backward students and fulfil their academic dreams. When compared to traditional learning enrolment v/s MOOCs, or Open Courseware enrolment, it shows students really do not know much about open educational resources (Alcorn, 2015). When we overcome this, we should conduct or organize more awareness programs such as workshops, conferences, or orientation programs to create awareness about OER. And implement it to add one subject of OER to the school students' curriculum. Open educational resources for school students will help future students learn about OER fully and clearly, and it should help them throughout their lifetime to continue learning.

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REFERENCES

- Alcorn, B., Christensen, G., & Kapur, D. (2015). Higher education and MOOCs in India and the Global South. *Change: The Magazine of Higher Learning*, 47(3), 42-49.
- Arunkumar, K. R., & Kannan, P. (2020). Awareness and use of Open Education Resources (OER) among PG students: A study of Alagappa University. In *Handbook of Research on Digital Content Management and Development in Modern Libraries* (pp. 21-35). IGI Global.
- Atkins, D. E., Brown, J. S., & Hammond, A. L. (2007). *A review of the open educational resources (OER) movement: Achievements, challenges, and new opportunities* (Vol. 164). Mountain View: Creative common.
- Baumeister, R. F., & Leary, M. R. (1997). Writing narrative literature reviews. *Review of general psychology*, 1(3), 311-320.

- Bulathwela, S., Perez-Ortiz, M., Yilmaz, E., & Shawe-Taylor, J. (2020, April). Truelearn: A family of bayesian algorithms to match lifelong learners to open educational resources. In *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence* (Vol. 34, No. 01, pp. 565-573).
- Chauhan, J. (2017). An overview of MOOC in India. *International Journal of Computer Trends and Technology*, 49(2), 111-120.
- Cronin, P., Ryan, F., & Coughlan, M. (2008). Undertaking a literature review: a step-by-step approach. *British journal of nursing*, 17(1), 38-43.
- Dinevski, D. (2008, June). Open educational resources and lifelong learning. In *ITI 2008-30th International Conference on Information Technology Interfaces* (pp. 117-122). IEEE.
- Halder, D. (2019). Potentials of unencumbered OER on lifelong learning: A critical review.
- Knoth, P. (2013). From open access metadata to open access content: two principles for increased visibility of open access content. In *Open Repositories 2013*. Retrieved from <http://oro.open.ac.uk/37824/>
- Lim, V., Wee, L., Teo, J., & Ng, S. (2017). Massive Open and Online Courses and Open Education Resources in Singapore. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1708.08743*.
- Mulder, F. (2007). The advancement of lifelong learning through open educational resources in an open and flexible (self) learning context. *Open Education Research*, 4, 1-10.
- Nagaiah, M., & Thanuskodi, S. (2021). Utilization of open educational resources (OERs) among college students affiliated to Alagappa university in India. *Linguistics and Culture Review*, 5(S3), 1384-1399.
- Nagaiah, M., Thanuskodi, S., & Alagu, A. AWARENESS AND USE OF OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES IN COLLEGE STUDENTS IN THE SIVAGANGA DISTRICT, TAMILNADU, INDIA.
- Nantha Kumar, S. (2011). Opportunities for adult learners through integrated e-learning.
- Sandanayake, T. C. (2019). Promoting open educational resources-based blended learning. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 16(1), 1-16.
- Yamada, T. (2014). OER Search and Retrieval in Asia: Preliminary Discussion for the Next Step. *OERin Lifelong Learning OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES*, 7.
- <https://en.unesco.org/themes/building-knowledge-societies/oer>